

Detailed procedures for the construction and setup of *Pinna nobilis* larval collectors applied by CNR-ISMAR (Venice) in the context of the Northern Adriatic

v. 01/04/2024

Tihana Marčeta, Andrea Sabino, Irene Guarneri, Marco Sigovini

CNR-ISMAR Venezia

This document provides a detailed description of both production and deployment of artificial larval collectors, adopted by CNR-ISMAR (Venice) to assess the larval recruitment of *Pinna nobilis*, as well as collect juveniles, in the Northern Adriatic. It builds upon and details consolidated protocols on the target species, in particular the one proposed by Kersting & Hendriks (2019), which has been widely applied across the Mediterranean (see Kersting *et al.*, 2020), as well as specific approaches for bivalve recruitment applied since early 2000s along the Veneto coasts (Chinellato *et al.*, 2006, Marceta *et al.*, 2022). Some adjustments were made to adapt to specific environmental conditions in the Northern Adriatic.

1) Details on collectors construction

The larval collector device consists of a main rope deployed vertically in the water column onto which a certain number of “collector bags” are attached in succession. In turn, each collector bag is made up of an outer net bag and a filler. The outer bag should have proper mesh size to allow water circulation, provide protection from predators and avoid the loss of organisms that have settled and grown inside the collector. The filler, which is made of entangled filaments or nets, constitutes the substrate for settlement and should allow adequate water circulation and consequent oxygenation, as well as maintain the overall shape. Each collector is identified by a plastic label placed inside the outer bag. Collector bags are tied to the rope and secured with cable ties.

The adopted outer bag is a 30 X 50 cm HDPE monofilament bag with a 4 mm mesh size. When considerable fouling colonization and high sedimentation rate is expected, such as in lagoons, a plastic tubular net for mussel breeding with a larger mesh size (2.5 cm measured as length of a whole stretched mesh), 1 m long and knotted at both ends, is preferred instead. The adopted filler is made up of 6 m long PP/HDPE tubular net for mussel breeding with larger mesh size (typically 10 cm measured as length of a whole stretched mesh), folded on itself in order to develop volume and offer resistance to compression. The resulting shape of the collector bags roughly approximates an irregular spheroid, with the major axis about 35-40 cm and the equatorial radius about 8-9 cm.

Both the outer bag and the filler materials are characterized by toughness and resistance, allowing to preserve the overall shape, to avoid twisting and squeezing and to reduce degradation and fragmentation (and consequent plastic input to the sea). They also allow for fast and accurate sorting operations. Once sorted and cleaned, the material, thanks to its durability, can be at least partly reused, so reducing costs and plastic waste.

2) Notes on collectors setup

The device setup could vary depending on local conditions. The main rope can either hang vertically from mussel farm lines or other maritime structures, either floating or fixed, with a ballast of adequate weight at the lower end, or it can be anchored to the seabed by ballast and maintained in a vertical position by floats/buoys. The presence of remarkable tides in the Northern Adriatic need to be taken into account when defining the setup, in particular within a network of sampling stations. The collector bags should be always kept submerged. In marine waters, it has been considered acceptable to set an upper depth limit of 5-6 m, which is the typical depth of mussel farms lines.

Collector bags are placed along the rope at a distance of 1 m from each other. They should be placed at least 1-2 m far from the seabed, in order to reduce the predation from benthic organisms and other possible disturbances. For each depth 3 (or more) replicates are deployed. Attention must be paid to the presence of nearby objects and structures capable of damaging the bags, including mussels or other fouling organisms. Specific criteria, either ecological or logistical, may be considered in order to optimize the effort, eg. by focusing on a narrow depth range.

3) Notes on deployment period, recovery and juvenile sorting

Pinna nobilis is a successive hermaphrodite, characterized by asynchronous gamete maturation. A succession of alternate spawning and fast gametogenesis occurs during the spawning period. According to a number of authors, the spawning period seems to range at least from May to August, however it may vary among different populations and depending on environmental conditions. About the Northern Adriatic area, in the Gulf of Trieste gonadal maturity has been recorded for the period between August and November (AMP Miramare, 2019). In the Lagoon of Venice, spawning has been observed since the month of June. Duration of the pelagic larval phase is still uncertain, roughly falling in the range of 10-30 days.

The Northern Adriatic is characterized by elevated productivity, which favors a considerable colonization of underwater structures, especially during spring and early summer, in particular in lagoons. In order to minimize the occlusion effect of fouling on the collector bags, the deployment of collectors has been set to the period between mid-June and the beginning of July. Collectors should undergo bimonthly monitoring, which may include the removal of significant fouling organisms from the outer surface of the collector bags. The collector devices should be retrieved after a period of about 5 months, however some delay, due to weather and sea conditions, may be inevitable. Collector bags need to be handled carefully and kept underwater until sorting. Filler should be unrolled and untangled gently, as the valves of juveniles are often very fragile. Juveniles are detached delicately and placed in water as soon as possible. Any juveniles settled onto the outer surface should be counted separately.

4) References

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This document has been produced within the TRECcap project (<https://www.ita-slo.eu/trecap>) supported by the Interreg VI-A Italy-Slovenia Cooperation Programme, financed by the European Regional Development Fund.